

Funded by
the European Union

Ref. Ares(2025)3509916 - 30/04/2025

D4.2 VISUAL IDENTITY AND PROMO PACKAGE OF THE PROJECT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101159516.

Project no: 101159516
Project acronym: widerAdvanceFacility
Project title: widerAdvance Facility – the Dissemination and Exploitation Facility for Widening projects
Call: HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-05
Start date of project: 01.01.2025
Duration: 48 months
Deliverable title: D4.2 (Visual identity and promo package of the project)
Due date of deliverable: 30.04.2025
Actual date of submission: 30.04.2025
Deliverable Lead Partner: EM
Dissemination level: Public

Author list

Name	Organization
Gloria Bevilacqua	EM
Veronika Kabai	EM

Document History

Version	Date	Note	Revised by
01	15.04.2025	First draft	WP partners
02	22.04.2025	Daft review	IPPT PAN
03	29.04.2025	Final version	WP partners

Disclaimer

The content of the publication herein is the sole responsibility of the publishers, and it does not necessarily represent the views expressed by the European Commission or its services.

While widerAdvance Facility is funded by the European Union, views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency (REA) can be held responsible for them.

While the information contained in the documents is believed to be accurate, the authors(s) or any other participant in the widerAdvance Facility consortium make no warranty of any kind with regard to this material including, but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose.

Neither the widerAdvance Facility Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be responsible for or liable in negligence or otherwise howsoever in respect of any inaccuracy or omission herein.

Without derogating from the generality of the foregoing neither the widerAdvance Facility Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be liable for any direct or indirect or consequential loss or damage caused by or arising from any information advice or inaccuracy or omission herein.

Copyright notice

© widerAdvance Facility Consortium, 2025-2028. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

Executive Summary

It is crucial for the successful communication and dissemination of a Horizon Europe project to present a consistent and innovative visual identity. Therefore, to attract and reach the various target groups, the widerAdvance Facility has developed tailored graphic elements. A suitable visual language and an appropriate design are key component of an efficient and engaging visual communication. The visual identity guidelines include these main graphic elements:

- Logo
- Colour scheme
- Font style
- Templates
- Graphics

The widerAdvance Facility's Visual Identity and Promo Package is designed to promote the consistent visual style of the project among its target audience. The document includes the main branding elements (logo, colour palette, typography, icons) and a preliminary list of promotional materials for the widerAdvance Facility. Further materials will be developed on the basis of this visual identity throughout the project in alignment with the evolving communication and dissemination strategy.

Table of Contents

1. widerAdvance Facility branding	8
1.1. Logo	8
1.2. Colours	9
1.3. Typography	10
1.4. Icons.....	11
1.5. Templates.....	11
1.5.1. Microsoft Office templates.....	11
1.5.2. Canva templates	12
1.6. Accessibility considerations.....	13
1.7. Brand monitoring and consistency	13
2. widerAdvance Facility promo package	14
2.1. Social media setup and branding.....	14
2.2. Communication and dissemination materials.....	16

List of Acronyms

CA	Consortium Agreement
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
CMYK	Cyan Magenta Yellow Black
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HEX	Hexadecimal (color code format)
PDF	Portable Document Format
PPT	PowerPoint Presentation
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RGB	Red Green Blue
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WP	Work Package

List of Figures

Figure 1 Logo variations in blue (horizontal, vertical, with tagline, logomark).....	8
Figure 2 Examples of logo misuses.....	9
Figure 3 Colour palette	10
Figure 4 Iconography	11
Figure 5 PowerPoint presentation template	12
Figure 6 Deliverable Word template.....	12
Figure 7 Screenshot of Canva	13
Figure 8 Screenshots of LinkedIn page and newsletter.....	15
Figure 9 Screenshot of Bluesky page.....	15
Figure 10 Screenshot of YouTube page	16
Figure 11 Email signature.....	16
Figure 12 Mockups of communication materials	17

1. widerAdvance Facility branding

widerAdvance Facility developed a distinctive visual identity to ensure the effective implementation of the project's dissemination and communication activities. Such a visual identity connects all of the project's partners together and makes the project more recognisable and understandable to the wider public.

A proper use of the widerAdvance Facility logo, typefaces and colour palette contributes to creating a familiar look of the project across all communication channels, reinforcing its quality image at the same time. A comprehensive branding guideline has been developed by EM and distributed to all partners at the beginning of the project for this purpose.

1.1. Logo

The logo featuring **interconnected dots forming a net in the shape of the letter "W"** represents networking, collaboration, and inclusivity.

The "W" symbolises Widening Participation, while the network of dots highlights the initiative's focus on building strong partnerships, sharing knowledge, and creating a unified, impactful research and innovation ecosystem.

The widerAdvance Facility logo must appear on all official communications and may not be modified in any way outside the variations specified in the official visual identity guidelines. Visual examples of proper and improper logo use are included in the guidelines and should be referenced to ensure brand consistency.

FIGURE 1 LOGO VARIATIONS IN BLUE (HORIZONTAL, VERTICAL, WITH TAGLINE, LOGOMARK)

FIGURE 2 EXAMPLES OF LOGO MISUSES

1.2. Colours

Branding colours play a crucial role in shaping identity, evoking emotions, and communicating a brand's values and mission at a glance.

The flowing colours have been selected to represent the widerAdvance Facility project:

- dark blue for stability
- lighter blue for collaboration
- yellow for energy
- bright green for growth

Together, they symbolise the mission to inspire innovation, foster inclusivity, and drive progress in European research.

A complete palette with HEX, RGB, and CMYK codes is included in the branding guidelines.

FIGURE 3 COLOUR PALETTE

1.3. Typography

Consistently following these font guidelines maintains a cohesive and professional brand identity, reinforcing recognition, trust and visual harmony, ensuring effective communication across all materials.

Primary font

Aa

Nunito Bold

The rounded primary font, used for titles and buttons, to create a welcoming and approachable feel.

Secondary Font

Aa

Montserrat Regular

The secondary font, selected for long texts and copy, ensuring optimal readability.

These fonts packages are distributed to all partners and are embedded in all templates provided.

1.4. Icons

The project’s visual identity includes a set of custom-designed icons available to all partners for use on the website, social media, and other promotional materials. These icons reflect project themes such as innovation, collaboration, and knowledge sharing. They will be updated as needed to support future content and maintain a cohesive and professional look throughout the project’s communications.

To further enhance clarity and recognition, a tailored set of icons will also be developed for the Facility’s key services — including the D&E Academy, IP consultancy, standardisation support, and synergy funding guidance. These service-specific icons will help visually distinguish and brand each core offer, making it easier for beneficiaries to understand and navigate the available support. This icon set will be designed in alignment with the overall visual language of the project and integrated into both online and print communication materials. They can be reused flexibly in service journey diagrams, leaflets, roll-ups, and presentations.

FIGURE 4 ICONOGRAPHY

1.5. Templates

1.5.1. Microsoft Office templates

Microsoft Word and PowerPoint templates have been created by EM for the consortium partners to be used for internal and external communication and dissemination. The branded templates are designed to give reports and presentations a consistent appearance and ensure uniformity, enhancing audience brand recognition and complying with EU visibility rules. Each

template includes the Horizon Europe disclaimer and project funding acknowledgment as required.

FIGURE 5 POWERPOINT PRESENTATION TEMPLATE

FIGURE 6 DELIVERABLE WORD TEMPLATE

1.5.2. Canva templates

EM designed and distributed Canva-based visual templates for use across partners' social media channels to promote project-related content (events, news, blog posts, consortium highlights, etc.). These templates will be regularly updated throughout the project to better respond to the partners' and target audiences' needs and to align with ongoing projects activities.

Using Canva ensures that all project partners maintain a consistent visual identity across platforms. The ready-to-use templates streamline the content creation process, making it faster and more efficient, even for those with limited design experience and/or in house capacity. Canva's collaborative features also allow for easy customisation while preserving key branding elements, ensuring a cohesive and professional look across all partner communications. This approach help enhancing brand recognition and maximising the project's visibility in a seamless and effective way.

The templates are stored in a shared workspace and editable copies are available for each partner.

FIGURE 7 SCREENSHOT OF CANVA

1.6. Accessibility considerations

Accessibility is a key component of effective communication. All visual identity elements and communication materials developed for the widerAdvance Facility take into account accessibility best practices to ensure inclusivity and reach across diverse audiences.

Key considerations include:

- High-contrast colour combinations are used to ensure text readability for users with visual impairments, following WCAG 2.1 AA standards.
- Sans-serif fonts (Nunito and Montserrat) are chosen for their legibility on both screen and print.
- Font sizes and line spacing are optimised for screen reading, with headings and body text clearly distinguished.
- Templates are designed to be screen-reader friendly, and graphics will include alt-text descriptions when published online.
- Canva and PowerPoint templates are structured using predefined styles, making it easier to preserve formatting and accessibility when shared or exported.
- Whenever possible, downloadable materials (PDFs, presentations) will include accessible tags and be tested for compatibility with assistive technologies.

These measures support the project's goal of making research communication inclusive, usable, and effective for all, including individuals with disabilities or limited digital literacy.

1.7. Brand monitoring and consistency

Maintaining brand consistency not only reinforces the visual identity of widerAdvance Facility but also contributes to a coherent and recognisable presence across Europe and beyond. It ensures that all communication materials uphold the quality and values of the project while meeting the European Commission's visibility requirements.

To ensure consistent and professional application of the widerAdvance Facility brand across all communication channels, EM will monitor the use of the branding and offer support to all partners needing feedback or clarification on the use of visual materials.

Any adjustments to the branding elements or templates (e.g. new icons, social media visuals, banner adaptations) will be clearly communicated to all partners via email and SharePoint to avoid outdated usage.

2. widerAdvance Facility promo package

The promo package of the widerAdvance Facility is designed to ensure a strong, recognisable, and consistent brand presence across all communication channels and project activities. This package combines digital and physical materials tailored to different audiences, communication goals, and project stages, supporting the broader dissemination and engagement strategy.

2.1. Social media setup and branding

LinkedIn and Bluesky profiles have been set up to share project news, updates, outcomes, newsletters, and blog posts, as well as curated content aligned with the project's themes.

EM designed platform-specific profile pictures and banners, ensuring they align with the project's branding guidelines. These visuals establish a professional and recognisable presence across platforms, reinforcing the project's identity and enhancing its visibility.

Editorial calendars and engagement guidelines are in development to support partners' outreach efforts.

FIGURE 8 SCREENSHOTS OF LINKEDIN PAGE AND NEWSLETTER

FIGURE 9 SCREENSHOT OF BLUESKY PAGE

FIGURE 10 SCREENSHOT OF YOUTUBE PAGE

2.2. Communication and dissemination materials

All the dissemination materials will follow the widerAdvance Facility visual identity, and they will be developed by EM. The first set of communication materials includes:

- PPT presentation which can be used by the partners in events, workshops, seminars
- Project leaflet (in digital and printed format)
- Project rollup
- Background for virtual meetings
- Email signature

FIGURE 11 EMAIL SIGNATURE

Additional communication and dissemination materials will be created as the project progresses based on needs and requests from partners and stakeholders, including:

- Infographics illustrating project objectives, services, and outcomes
- Social media assets for campaigns and thematic weeks
- Short video introducing the Facility's services
- Project media kit including logos, factsheets, boilerplate text, and contact information for media use.

Preference will be given to digital formats to minimise environmental impact, with print used strategically when necessary. All the materials will be available online on the project website in a downloadable format for external distribution and on the project internal SharePoint for the project consortium.

FIGURE 12 MOCKUPS OF COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

Follow us on:

@widerAdvance

widerAdvance Facility

@wideradvance.bsky.social

Learn more:

www.widerAdvance.eu